

APPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY**Radev R.***Doctor of Commodity Science, Chief Assistant Professor
University of Economics
Varna, Bulgaria***Abstract**

The purpose of this article is to applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the textile industry. To achieve the scientific goal in this article are used descriptive-analytical method, study of various scientific literature about applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the textile industry, systematic approach, comparative analysis, method of observation, induction, deduction, etc. In conclusion, it has been established that at the current stage of development of digital technologies and innovations, artificial intelligence (AI) is of increasing importance for the development of the textile industry. With the implementation, integration and development of artificial intelligence (AI), companies in the textile industry can optimize their processes, activities, textile products, quality control, thereby increasing the efficiency of their business organization.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, AI, textile, textile industry.

Introduction

The textile industry plays a key role in the economy, as the sector is based on the correct selection of quality textile raw materials, the composition of yarns, which in the weaving process form fabrics from different textile materials, and in the cutting process, textile products are formed, which are previously dyed. A huge variety of different types of textile products are produced using different technological schemes and processes, as well as complex finishing and dyeing procedures. To improve quality, increase production and reduce operating costs, internal control over production is exercised, which leads to shorter lead times, AI is used, which is quickly becoming a key tool for textile companies [1].

Before 1949, computers were not intelligent, as they could not write commands, but they could execute them. Between 1957 and 1974, artificial intelligence (AI) developed, increasing computer memory, speed, cost, and accessibility. AI enables machines to perform various tasks that humans must perform with their natural intelligence. In 1950, AI creators Marvin Minsky and John McCarthy defined artificial intelligence, which allows machines to achieve certain goals by analyzing vast amounts of unstructured data in the form of text, images, and audio. AI is relevant to almost every industry and will continue to grow strongly in the future. Machine learning and computer algorithms have been widely used in testing in the textile industry since the 1980s. Testing and quality control using AI can be defined through image processing, automation, training, and neural networks. The majority of the textile industry these days uses computer-aided machines in the production process, to create designs and access data to improve efficiency [2].

Artificial intelligence (AI) is being used in more and more industries, and the textile industry is no exception. The implementation and integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in the textile industry is transforming a number of activities related to conventional production, design and interaction with consumers of textile products. Through the use of AI, it becomes possible to increase efficiency, sustainability and innovation in the textile industry. The advantage of AI in the

textile industry is the ability to process large amounts of data and, based on them, make decisions that optimize the production process and design of textile products. In addition, artificial intelligence in the textile industry is also useful in terms of defect detection, accuracy in predicting consumer demand, accuracy in supply chain management, waste minimization, optimization of resource use and sustainability in the textile industry [3].

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a powerful tool for increasing productivity in the textile industry, developing design concepts, predicting upcoming trends, detecting defects, assessing quality and evaluating the colors of textile products. AI enables the improvement of the quality of textile products, reduces labor costs, increases production speed, and its application is likely to increase in the future [4].

The textile industry has increasingly started to use artificial intelligence (AI) methods, as it can gain a lot from AI systems that can help optimize various processes in production, quality, statistical control, information, costs and output. AI develops and applies various models and analyzes huge volumes of quantitative data, allowing their optimal use [1]. The reason for research on the application of AI in the textile industry is its increasing penetration into companies.

The purpose of this article is to study to applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the textile industry.

Methodology

To achieve the scientific goal in this article are used descriptive-analytical method, study of various scientific literature about applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the textile industry, systematic approach, comparative analysis, method of observation, induction, deduction, etc..

Results and discussion

An important aspect of textile production is the quality control of manufactured textile products. Early identification of defects is essential for ensuring the quality of textile products, which provides a competitive advantage to companies. Quality determination is carried out by inspecting textile products through visual

and tactile inspection for defects, which creates challenges and opportunities for human error. This *enables artificial intelligence (AI) to be applied in the textile industry* through image processing, computer vision and machine learning to *detect defects with better speed, accuracy and reliability* compared to inspection by quality inspectors. The study presents the different types of defects in textile products that occur at different stages of production. In addition, the advantages and disadvantages of conventional and automated approaches are evaluated, emphasizing the key role of achieving high accuracy in identifying defects in textile products. The study also examines the integration of AI technologies, such as high-resolution cameras, real-time surveillance systems, in the quality control processes of textile products in the context of sustainability, optimization of production processes and the profitability of companies in the textile industry in the context of digital transformation [5].

Another study presents the *integration and implementation of a system (artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision) for textile defect detection, tailored for the textile industry*. The detection of defects (holes, color bleeding and creases on plain-colored cotton and linen fabrics without patterns) is essential for ensuring the quality of textiles in textile production, as manual inspection is prone to errors, making it ineffective. When studying the quality of textiles, each detected defect is registered with a location, class, credibility assessment and a unique identifier, which are needed for further quality analysis. The analysis is performed by two cameras, which are located about 1 m from the textiles under controlled lighting conditions in a real industrial environment [6].

The study analyzed *the applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in the textile industry*, which include various techniques for textile yarn analysis, textile fabric inspection, improving the productivity of the production process, using neural networks and artificial vision. Regarding the *advantages* of using AI in the textile industry, it was found that all these techniques allow for better analysis of textile yarn and identification of defects in textile products. A *disadvantage* of the AI used in the textile industry is the fact that they do not have a standardized algorithm that can be used, which makes their application more difficult [7].

The textile industry in India is the second largest employment sector and the largest contributor to the country's GDP. The study found that the textile industry is lagging behind in terms of technological innovation. The introduction of AI in the textile industry will lead to increased efficiency by quickly bringing diverse ideas to market at lower levels of labor and costs in textile production, which will optimize the supply chain

and increase consumer satisfaction. In addition, AI will help develop and maintain sustainability, which will help manufacturers and distributors adapt to market demand. The article concludes that *the implementation of AI in the textile industry has led to improved efficiency of the production process in companies by automating design processes, increasing worker productivity and reducing the time to develop textile products* [8].

The application of AI in the textile industry through mechatronics has existed for a long time, with its applications related to the design of textile machines (weaving and LAN weaving systems, 3D interlacing; yarn tension compensation; texturing; spinning: measurement automation and diagnostics, knowledge-based expert systems; automated garment production and assembly; and garment manufacturing). Mechatronic design in the textile industry contains the opportunity to optimize the concept of mechatronics and design methodology and the impact of technological advances on the concept of mechatronics, which has a multifaceted application in the textile industry and leads to process optimization in companies [9].

In today's environment, the majority of consumers prefer to wear textiles that are in line with the latest fashion trends. For this reason, textile companies need to meet the growing consumer demand for a variety of textile products, which should be achieved by increasing production capacity and improving operational efficiency through AI. *Companies are increasingly using AI* and its various tools to improve their processes and related activities. AI is beneficial to companies by establishing significant relationships with demand forecasting, decision making, and textile supply. The results of the study show that AI is highly correlated with all dependent variables. Regression tests also prove that AI has a significant impact on demand forecasting, decision making, and textile supply for textile companies [10].

The study presents a *thorough and detailed analysis on the determination and evaluation of the color of textiles made in the laboratory department of a textile dyeing company in Turkey*. In the study of the textile industry company on the finishing of textiles, it was found that classical processes were used to determine the target color of textiles. Then, it is mentioned how the data obtained with the spectrophotometer is used to *evaluate the color of textiles using machine learning methods and artificial neural networks (AI)*. The results obtained show that the data obtained from the hyperspectral camera is evaluated by a long-term short-term memory model, since the spectrophotometer does not give such an accurate result [11].

Figure 1. AI colour of textile products [1].

The study demonstrates that *the application of AI in the textile industry enables significant improvements in efficiency, speed, and reliability in textile material classification, textile defect identification, color detection, and pattern recognition.* The integration of AI in the textile industry enables the improvement of analytical analyses and sensors, which allow for better prediction of certain processes and activities, as a result of which reasoned decisions are made based on real-time analyses, which provides opportunities for automated selection, monitoring, quality control and operational efficiency. The study emphasizes the role of AI in the development of the textile industry into a smarter, more efficient and sustainable industry, encouraging new solutions to neutralize disadvantages [12].

The overwhelming majority of the textile industry is managed by people who are not well-trained in information technology, including AI. Future textile professionals can be better prepared to understand information technology and AI, which will help digitize processes in the textile industry and better manage it while identifying the numerous advantages that AI offers. *AI and its related technologies and their benefits are part of the rapidly developing technologies that have the potential to optimize the activities of the textile industry* [13].

The textile industry in India is increasingly using AI and its applications to optimize their operations and activities. A study on the impact of AI has found its significant role in demand forecasting, sales forecasting and order process management. The study concluded that AI has a major impact on the ordering processes, demand forecasting and sales forecasting of textile companies, which helps in optimizing their overall operations [14].

A study has highlighted the *crucial importance of AI in the textile industry in today's environment.* AI has a positive impact on manufacturing, design innovation, e-commerce, supply chain management by improving operational efficiency and providing opportunities for sustainability. The study identifies the extent of AI application in the textile industry in the context of fashion sustainability. Despite optimistic forecasts regarding the use of AI in the textile industry, available solutions are being used to a limited extent, as companies put economic goals above sustainable development goals [15].

Smart textiles are created by improving technology and implementing innovative textile applications in the textile industry, which is in line with consumer preferences. With the help of AI hardware (neuromorphic computing) and various software modules that mimic the processing capabilities and properties of the neural networks of the human nervous system, the textile sector is enabled to implement innovative and emerging technologies, which contributes to the development of e-textiles. This new generation of AI is rapidly gaining great importance for the textile industry, as it generates the use of new innovative applications. In a *study of the progress of AI in the textile industry for e-textiles*, it was found that when combined with basic architectural elements of artificial neural networks, neuromorphic computing (2D and 3D structures) can *influence new scientific developments in the e-textile sector* [16].

A study found that AI is widely used in more and more areas of business life, which includes the textile industry. With the help of AI, computer parameters for the textile industry have been developed, which will help the emergence of textile garment correction tech-

nology. The article discusses the trend in the development of AI technology and the establishment of computer parameters for textile garments in combination with their development. A textile garment correction system has been created, which can provide a useful reference for the development of AI in the textile industry. Experimental data from the study show that with *optimized design of computer parameters, the creation of an AI-based textile garment correction system helps to integrate AI into textile garment production and improve the efficiency of company management* [17].

AI has great advantages that enable *better system management*, which can lead to *better quality of textiles and better operational efficiency*. The application of AI in textile operations in the textile industry can help solve various problems with good precision. Neural networks, as part of AI, can process various images of textiles, and the computer system can learn billions of combinations of errors that can occur in textiles based on data programming and machine learning. In this way, AI, through a pre-programmed system and image processing, helps to identify defects in yarn. In addition, defects in fabrics can be detected by AI image processing, and through nonlinear regression and ANN (artificial neural networks) can study the structural data of the fabric (bending stiffness and air permeability). AI is also effective in detecting and identifying defects in clothing, which allows for increased levels of production and quality of clothing. *The study also found that the expert system built with the help of AI gives more accurate results than those of human experts, who make more mistakes*. In the case of difficult detection of defects in textile products during dyeing, the expert system built with AI gives more accurate results. ANN and machine learning can be used to prepare recipes for dyeing textile products, as well as to determine colors and shades. AI can also help in identifying textile fibers, increasing productivity, creating safer working conditions in the textile industry [18].

Another study also confirmed that *AI provides new and better opportunities for the development of the textile industry, which has a positive impact on efficiency*. AI influences the various stages of production, optimizing fabric production, color matching and better controlling the quality of textile products. With the development of AI technologies, manufacturers use data to make optimal decisions in real time. With the help of AI, the virtual representation of supply chains is realized with the possibility of reducing textile waste, lower costs and a positive impact on the environment, which is in line with sustainability policies. The integration, transformation of innovations with the help of AI in the textile industry allows companies to increase efficiency. Thanks to AI, textile production has been transformed, including yarn production, fabric quality assessment and color management of textile products, fabric classification, pattern making and supply chain management. AI generates new designs, optimizes processes, predicts trends, and enables the creation of smart clothing with health monitoring capabilities. In conclusion, the authors of the study believe that the *impact of AI on the textile industry is generating innovation, efficiency, and creative opportunities*, while also

prompting critical ethical discussions, which is a prerequisite for future research [19].

After the scientific study on the application of AI in the textile industry, it was found that there is a huge impact, expressed in detecting defects at a better speed; integrating and implementing a system (artificial intelligence (AI) and computer vision) for detecting defects in textiles; identifying the advantages and disadvantages of using AI; implementing AI in the textile industry and improving efficiency; exploring the application of AI in the textile industry through mechatronics; more often using AI in companies; in-depth and detailed analysis of textile color determination and evaluation; evaluating textile color using machine learning methods and artificial neural networks (AI); the application of AI in the textile industry and the opportunities for significant improvements; optimizing AI activities in the textile industry; increasingly using AI and its applications to optimize operations and activities in the textile industry; the crucial importance of AI in the textile industry in today's environment; the progress of AI in the textile industry for electronic textiles; the impact on new scientific developments in the electronic textile sector; optimized design of computer parameters, the creation of an AI-based textile garment correction system, helping to integrate AI into textile garment production and improve the efficiency of company management; better system management, which can lead to better textile quality and better operational efficiency; it has been found that the expert system built with the help of artificial intelligence produces more accurate results than those of human experts who make more mistakes; AI provides new and better opportunities for the development of the textile industry, which has a positive effect on efficiency; the impact of AI on the textile industry is to generate innovation, efficiency and creative opportunities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it has been established that at the current stage of development of digital technologies and innovations, artificial intelligence (AI) is of increasing importance for the development of the textile industry. With the implementation, integration and development of artificial intelligence (AI), companies in the textile industry can optimize their processes, activities, textile products, quality control, thereby increasing the efficiency of their business organization.

References

1. Bhargava, G. (2018). Artificial intelligence and its implementation in the textile industry. *Rigeo*, 8, (3), 613-625.
2. Bansode, P., Goyal, P. (2024). Artificial Intelligence in Textile and Fashion World. *International Journal of Research -GRANTHAALAYAH*, 12, (5), 32–42. doi:10.29121/granthaalayah.v12.i5.2024.5626.
3. Kumar, T. S., Muthuvelammai, S., Jayachandran, N. (2024). AI in Textiles: A Review of Emerging Trends and Applications. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET)*, ISSN: 2321-9653; IC Value: 45.98; SJ Impact Factor: 7.538, Volume 12 Issue IX

Sep 2024- Available at www.ijraset.com,
<https://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2024.64404>.

4. Anwer, H., Ali, M., Jamshaid, H. (2024). Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Textiles and Fashion. In: Jamshaid, H., Dad, A. (eds) Creative Textile Industry. SDGs and Textiles. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-97-3802-1_8.

5. Ozek, A., Seckin, M., Demircioglu, P., Bogrekci, I. (2025). Artificial Intelligence Driving Innovation in Textile Defect Detection. *Textiles*, 5, 12, <https://doi.org/10.3390/textiles5020012>.

6. Machado, R., Barros, L. A. M., Vieira, V., Silva, F.D.d., Costa, H., Carvalho, V. (2025). Textile Defect Detection Using Artificial Intelligence and Computer Vision—A Preliminary Deep Learning Approach. *Electronics*, 14, 3692. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics14183692>.

7. Pereira, F., Carvalho, V., Vasconcelos, R., Soares, F. (2022). A Review in the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Textile Industry. In: Machado, J., Soares, F., Trojanowska, J., Yildirim, S. (eds) Innovations in Mechatronics Engineering. *icieng 2021. Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-79168-1_34.

8. Reenu, Singh, S., Vig, S., Dwivedi, S. (2024). Impact of uses of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Textile Industry in India. In 2024 15th International Conference on Computing Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT), (pp. 1-9), IEEE, DOI: 10.1109/ICCCNT61001.2024.10725995.

9. Elnashar, E., Ahmed, A. A. M., Elnashar, A. E. (2023). Artificial Intelligence Applications in the Textile Industries Using Mechatronics. *Latest Trends in Textile and Fashion Designing*, 5, 914-927, DOI: 10.32474/LTTFD.2023.05.000215.

10. Khan, H. (2021). The application of artificial intelligence in the supply chains of textile industries. *Journal for Business Education and Management*, 1, (2), 21-34, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.56596/jbem.v1i2.64>.

11. Şahin, İ. C., Eyüpoğlu, C. (2024). Textile dyeing process and dyeing recipe prediction using artificial intelligence. *İstanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi*

Teknoloji ve Uygulamalı Bilimler Dergisi, 6, (2), 1-20, <https://doi.org/10.56809/icujtas.1293563>.

12. Hossain, M. M., Roy, A., Nahiduzzaman, M. (2025). Modernizing Textile Industry Operations with Artificial Intelligence. *Applied IT & Engineering*, 3, (1), 1-8, <https://doi.org/10.25163/engineering.3110230>.

13. Parachuru, R. (2023). A quick look at the recent advances, current state of utilization and expected future usage of artificial intelligence (AI) in the global textile manufacturing industry. *Journal of Textile Engineering and Fashion Technology*, 9, (6), 190-194, DOI: 10.15406/jteft.2023.09.00355.

14. Rana, D. (2024). The Impact of Artificial Intelligence in the Supply Chain Performance for Textile Industry. *Business Transforma on & Sustainable Innova on: An Edge to the Global Circular Economy*, 1.

15. Bienkowska, J. (2025). The effects of artificial intelligence on the fashion industry—Opportunities and challenges for sustainable transformation. *Sustainable Development*, 33, (3), 3774-3790, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.3312>.

16. Cleary, F., Srisa-An, W., Henshall, D. C., Balasubramaniam, S. (2023). Emerging AI technologies inspiring the next generation of E-textiles. *IEEE Access*, 11, 56494-56508, DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3282184.

17. Yan, L., Liu, W. (2021). Garment textile correction system based on artificial intelligence under computer parameter optimization design. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1881, No. 4, p. 042017), IOP Publishing, DOI 10.1088/1742-6596/1881/4/042017.

18. Sikka, M. P., Sarkar, A., Garg, S. (2022). Artificial intelligence (AI) in textile industry operational modernization. *Research Journal of Textile and Apparel*, Emerald Publishing Limited, 1560-6074, DOI 10.1108/RJTA-04-2021-0046.

19. Sharma, S., Subbarao, N. (2025). Artificial Intelligence, A new weaver in textile Industry. *Asian Textile Journal z December 2024-January 2025 z 60*, 59-64.